

PABLO ANTÚNEZ

**DRAMA IN D-FLAT
MAJOR FOR A BIRD**

ENGLISH — DEUTSCH — ESPAÑOL

POEMS

Drama in D-flat major for a bird

Pablo Antúnez

Göttingen, Germany —July, 2019

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